

APPROACHES TO FOOD WASTE REDUCTION AND FOOD SOVEREIGNTY ENHANCEMENT: THE CASE OF UZBEKISTAN.

Shakhlokhon Usmanova

Master's student, International Agriculture University, Tashkent, Uzbekistan.
shaxlo2202@gmail.com

Conference name: "Food Security: Global and National Issues" (Oziq-Ovqat Xavfsizligi: Global va Milliy Muammolar). 14.10.2025.

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17452774>

Abstract: Food security and food sovereignty are becoming a pressing issue in our country today. The percentage of food waste and losses is increasing, and these results are an obstacle to the development of food sustainability. In addition, the level of import dependence also makes it impossible to increase food sovereignty. First, this study provides a broader definition of the concepts of food waste and food loss and food sovereignty, their essence and importance in the food sector. In addition, it examines the problems of food waste and food sovereignty in our country and presents appropriate international and local solutions. This article was created using secondary data, various global and local statistics, journals, articles and government reports, as well as political news. In addition, the research highlights methods for improving food waste and food sovereignty based on modern technologies that have achieved results internationally.

Key words: Food security, food sovereignty, food waste, recycling waste, food lost, supply chain, production, logistics, consumption, consumer behaviour,

Introductoin

Today, as the population growth rate increases, the demand for food products has increased. Unfortunately, more than 783 million people in the world are currently suffering from hunger (Environment, 2024). Providing the population with agricultural products and safe food in every region has become one of the main directions. Strategies such as ensuring sustainability in the food industry and reducing food waste and food sovereignty can reduce hunger and poverty worldwide and increase the well-being of countries. Food waste affects the environment and resource use beyond human activities. Greenhouse gas emissions, which are harmful to the environment, account for 8-10 percent of the total index (Food Waste Index Report 2024 | FAO, n.d.). Food sovereignty also promotes the idea that developing countries, such as Uzbekistan, should increase food security and take full control measures in the food system to ensure safe products. As in the rest of the world, food loss and food waste occur at every stage

of the food supply chain in our country, and it is impossible to eliminate it. To prevent this, we can only reduce the level of waste and losses. Disruptions in the supply chain, deficiencies in infrastructure, as well as the incompetence of farmers and supply chain participants and negative consumer habits play a major role in the occurrence of food waste. Statistics show that one-third of all food produced worldwide is lost or wasted before it reaches the consumer. This is equivalent to the amount of food produced in an area the size of China (Goodwin & Lipinski, 2024).

The purpose of this report is to study the problems and shortcomings in food waste and food sovereignty in the food and agricultural sectors of the Republic of Uzbekistan, and to present and analyze solutions that are being proposed worldwide and are suitable for the conditions of Uzbekistan.

First, if we look at the terms food waste and food lost, food lost is the quantity and quality of loss that occur at various stages in the supply chain before reaching the consumer, i.e. during the cultivation, harvesting, processing, storage, logistics process, and before being sold in the store. Food waste is food products that appear after human consumption, that is, wasted food products. Food waste occurs when the consumer wears out or overconsumes the products he has purchased and when the excess food on the table is not eaten (Eshmatov, 2025). The term food sovereignty was first coined by La Via Campesina in 1996 as a movement of rural indigenous peoples and farmers and has since been linked to many organizations and social movements. Food sovereignty is not just about the food system, but also includes rights such as cooperation, justice, free markets and solidarity (Food Sovereignty - Friends of the Earth International, n.d.). Food sovereignty is a food system in which people everywhere have the right to produce, sell, and consume agricultural and food products, considering environmental, social, and geographical aspects. It is also a pillar that ensures our past, present, and future (What Is Food Sovereignty?, n.d.). Smallholder farmers and local food producers play a key role in food sovereignty, and the challenges they face today are increasing. The main thing is that they account for 80% of the main production (Farmer Managed Seed Systems - Why Controlling Seeds Is a Threat to Food Sovereignty | FAO, n.d.). The food sovereignty system aims to further promote and support the participation of women, smallholder farmers, and local communities in the food industry.

Research Methods

This study used a variety of data sources to identify the causes of food waste in Uzbekistan, to propose measures to reduce it, and to identify strategies to strengthen food sovereignty. The data collection phase analyzed reports and statistics from various organizations related to the food sector in Uzbekistan, as well as international levels of food waste. The study focused on waste and losses in the food supply chain in Uzbekistan, from production, storage, transportation, and consumption, and its impact on food sovereignty. The data sources were formed based on peer-reviewed journals, articles, reports, and open data from international and local organizations. The state of food waste and food sovereignty in Uzbekistan also included real data, considering the social lifestyle of the population and the political system of the state.

Findings and Discussion

According to economic calculations, the annual loss of food waste is estimated at \$1 trillion. Unfortunately, if these losses were not there, there would probably be less hunger in the world (Cederberg & Sonesson, 2011). The main sources of food waste are retail, markets, restaurants, and consumer rejection of products at home. More specifically, it occurs when products are bought more than they need, when eating unhealthy foods, and when there are some defects in the appearance of the product. A better way to deal with food waste is not to landfill it, but to recycle it or mobilize it for industrial and agricultural purposes. More specifically, the industrial use of products that are not suitable for human consumption, such as biofuels and biopolymers for agricultural land, is effective. According to the information provided, methods such as feeding people suffering from hunger with edible food products, processing them, feeding animals, using them as fuel, and safely transporting them have been proposed.

Solutions aimed at consumer behavior to reduce food waste:

- Planned shopping,
- Constant use of refrigerators, i.e., paying attention to the quality and good storage of purchased products until consumption.
- Creative use of remaining products.
- Cooking, mixing, and chopping fruits and vegetables that have slightly changed in appearance. Instead of throwing them in the trash, use them in the preparation of other products such as canned sauces and jams (Fight Climate Change by Preventing Food Waste, n.d.).

Food waste classification is important in reducing waste. It allows for automated identification and classification of waste levels through in-depth

analysis. One of the innovative approaches to reducing food waste is the Food Waste Image (FWI) technology, which uses images of more than 50,000 food products in a dataset to identify agricultural products that are unfit for consumption and other defects through each product label. This technology works based on artificial intelligence and deep learning (Mazloumian et al., 2020). Similar innovations based on advanced technology could effectively manage, identify and classify food waste in hotels, cafes and other business centers. Classified food products are processed into useful and edible products. According to scientific research and tests, fruit and vegetable peels can be used as prebiotics in medicine. Often, citrus peels have antioxidant properties. Such post-processing can also be used to determine the nutritional value of bakery products, such as fiber and other powders, and fruit and vegetable peels. It is also used in beverages. The additive is also used to obtain natural food colors and pigments (Fruits and Vegetables Peel's Incorporation in Different Food Products', n.d.). Although this technology was not popular, it was a natural and adaptable method to be used in various conditions. Recycling waste products using these and other methods mentioned above will help reduce the level of waste. Strategies used in the United States to increase food sovereignty served as the basis for developing this area. They used workshops with residents in the United States and Canada to increase community knowledge about the food system, develop cross-cultural communication skills, implement traditional product production and direct consumption, and other community-related programs (Gutierrez et al., 2023). Food sovereignty ensures the right to freely produce food products in agriculture and the food industry, supporting the local population and smallholder farmers. These include mainly agriculture, livestock, fisheries and other food sectors. In 2023, Uzbekistan produced just under 9 million tons of grain, 11.6 million tons of vegetables, 3.6 million tons of potatoes and other products (How Uzbekistan solves the problems of ensuring food security In the... | Vladimir Norov, n.d.). It should be noted that the main participants in the total production are local farmers and peasants. According to the research data studied, the following recommendations for increasing food sovereignty will effectively help improve the system: first of all, it includes principles such as supporting local production, applying modern agrotechnology in agriculture and replacing old infrastructure, improving the knowledge and skills of the population and society, improving the supply chain infrastructure, and making political decisions that are appropriate for society. According to ReFed, 120 million meals are wasted without being eaten

or sold, which not only negatively affects the country's GDP, but also negatively affects the environment due to the release of harmful methane gases from wasted food. (Food Waste Data—Causes & Impacts, n.d.).

Let's look at the processes that lead to food loss and waste one by one

Manufacturing	Handling and storing	Processing and packaging	Market and distribution	Consumption
During harvest	Logistics, storage and sorting	During industrial and local reprocessing and packaging	During the retail market and local market, wholesale process	In restaurants, markets, homes, caterers,

Figure 1 based on (Cederberg & Sonesson, 2011).

In developed countries, food waste is more of a concern. The main factors for this are the consumer's excessive and excessive demand for products. For example, in high-income countries such as Europe and the United States, people have a habit of buying food products for pleasure. It is not important for such people whether they consume the purchased products later or not.

The fact is that excessive buying increases the risk of food waste, that is, due to the long time they are in the refrigerator, their quality deteriorates and becomes waste, in addition, consumer behavior also includes a variety of choices. To be more precise, each customer in restaurants and eating places chooses food based on their own preferences. The variety in this process can also lead to the use of many products by one person and, in some sense, some products being wasted during the preparation process.

Based on the collected data, it can be analyzed that the level of food loss and waste and food sovereignty are interrelated. When food sovereignty increases, food waste and loss problems are less common in regions. Because increasing the rights, freedoms and comprehensive opportunities of rural livelihoods to produce food is part of the basic principles of food sovereignty and ensures growth in the country's food system. For example, during the COVID-19 pandemic, areas with weak local food systems faced challenges and problems, while areas with developed food sovereignty were able to recover more quickly in providing food

to their populations (Impacts of COVID-19 on Food Security and Nutrition: Developing Effective Policy Responses to Address the Hunger and Malnutrition Pandemic, n.d.). After independence, Uzbekistan achieved food sovereignty, that is, it gradually began to provide the population with food products through its domestic production capabilities, which is 90%. This means that the population's ability to satisfy its own food demand has freed it from dependence on the food production of other countries, as was the case during the former Soviet Union. Our country also ranks 96th out of 113 countries in the global food security index. (Global Food Security Index (GFSI), 2025).

Conclusions

In short, food waste and food sovereignty are interrelated global problems. Their impact affects not only the external environment and the economy, but also the social and, most importantly, the well-being of the population and all sectors. This report explained the main differences between food loss and waste and proposed the causes of these problems and appropriate solutions to them. Since the topic is about reducing food waste and improving food sovereignty, the main idea of the report was to provide all the terms, causes and implications of food waste.

Despite the many strategies and solutions proposed for food waste, the level of waste continues to rise worldwide. Based on the data collected, the main stage of food waste occurs at the consumer stage after purchase and is completely dependent on people's food consumption behavior. In addition, the issue of increasing food sovereignty is also largely dependent on government decisions. Therefore, everyone should start preventing food waste at their own table. Informing all public representatives in country about the negative consequences of food waste, will also serve as an incentive to change consumer habits

Reference list:

1. Cederberg, C., & Sonesson, U. (2011). Global food losses and food waste: Extent, causes and prevention; study conducted for the International Congress Save Food! at Interpack 2011, [16 - 17 May], Düsseldorf, Germany (J. Gustavsson, Ed.). International Congress Save Food!, Rome. Food and Agriculture Organization of the United Nations.
2. Environment, U. N. (2021, April 3). UNEP Food Waste Index Report 2021 | UNEP - UN Environment Programme. <https://www.unep.org/resources/report/unep-food-waste-index-report-2021>

3. Farmer Managed Seed Systems—Why Controlling Seeds Is a Threat to Food Sovereignty | FAO. (n.d.). Retrieved 28 April 2025, from <http://www.fao.org/agroecology/database/detail/en/c/1709845/>
4. Fight climate change by preventing food waste. (n.d.). World Wildlife Fund. Retrieved 29 April 2025, from <https://www.worldwildlife.org/stories/fight-climate-change-by-preventing-food-waste>
5. Food Sovereignty: Friends of the Earth International. (n.d.). Retrieved 28 April 2025, from <https://www.foei.org/what-we-do/food-sovereignty/>
6. Food Waste Data—Causes & Impacts. (n.d.). Retrieved 28 April 2025, from <https://refed.org/food-waste/the-problem/>
7. Food Waste Index Report 2024 | FAO. (n.d.). Retrieved 28 April 2025, from <https://www.fao.org/family-farming/detail/en/c/1681058/>
8. Global Food Security Index (GFSI). (2025, April 28). Global Food Security Index (GFSI). <https://impact.economist.com/sustainability/project/food-security-index>
9. Goodwin, L., & Lipinski, B. (2024). How Much Food Does the World Really Waste? What We Know — and What We Don't. <https://www.wri.org/insights/how-much-food-does-the-world-waste>
10. Gutierrez, B. V., Kaloostian, D., & Redvers, N. (2023). Elements of Successful Food Sovereignty Interventions within Indigenous Communities in the United States and Canada: A Systematic Review. *Current Developments in Nutrition*, 7(9), 101973. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cdnut.2023.101973>
11. How Uzbekistan solves the problems of ensuring food security In the... | Vladimir Norov. (n.d.). Retrieved 29 April 2025, from https://www.linkedin.com/posts/vladimirnorov_how-uzbekistan-solves-the-problems-of-ensuring-activity-7262204406954147841-JOHY
12. Impacts of COVID-19 on food security and nutrition: Developing effective policy responses to address the hunger and malnutrition pandemic. (n.d.).
- 13.
14. Mazloumian, A., Rosenthal, M., & Gelke, H. (2020). Deep Learning for Classifying Food Waste (No. arXiv:2002.03786). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2002.03786>
15. (PDF) Fruits and vegetables peel's incorporation in different food products: A review. (n.d.). ResearchGate. Retrieved 29 April 2025, from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/372958429_Fruits_and_vegetables_peel's_incorporation_in_different_food_products_A_review

16. 15)What is Food Sovereignty? (n.d.). La Via Campesina - EN. Retrieved 28 April 2025, from <https://viacampesina.org/en/what-is-food-sovereignty/>

